

The Effect of *Toxoplasma gondii* Infection on Hematological and Biochemical Tests in Women infected with the Parasite

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the effect of toxoplasmosis infection on haematological and biochemical parameters in women infected with the parasite and to compare them with the control group. Ninety blood samples were collected from women at Tikrit teaching hospital and several private laboratories between September 1, 2024, and September 1, 2025. The women ranged in age from 18 to 40 years. The study aimed to evaluate haematological tests (Hb, Pcv, Wbc), liver enzymes (AST, ALT and ALP), and lipids (cholesterol, triglycerides and HDL) in infected women and compare them with the control group. The statistical analysis revealed a significant decrease in blood tests (Hb, Pcv, Wbc) by 9.0 ± 1.6 , $.35 \pm 1.9$, 14.3 ± 2.1 respectively, compared to the control group by 13.17 ± 1.1 , 39.0 ± 2.7 , 7.23 ± 1.71 respectively. A significant increase was also observed in liver enzymes (AST, ALT, ALP) by 75.78 ± 27.86 , 6937.38 ± 2085.61 , 102.34 ± 26.06 respectively, compared to the control group by 2.30 ± 0.81 , 391.80 ± 284.10 , 22.34 ± 10.46 . Finally, a significant increase was found in the lipid profile (cholesterol, triglycerides, and HDL) $.230 \pm 30$, 225.8 ± 33.4 , 38.9 ± 6.1 respectively compared with the control group by 162.7 ± 42.3 , 145.7 ± 9.2 , 33.7 ± 5.8 respectively.

Keywords: *Toxoplasma gondii*, Haematological test, liver enzyme, lipid profile.

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Introduction

Toxoplasmosis is a zoonotic disease caused by the parasite *Toxoplasma gondii*, an obligate intracellular protozoan. Many members of the feline family are considered definitive and intermediate hosts for the parasite. Humans and warm-blooded animals are the intermediate hosts (Mahmood et al., 2022). Humans become infected through the ingestion of food or water contaminated with egg sacs shed in the faeces of infected cats or by consuming undercooked or raw meat containing tissue cysts. Congenital transmission from an infected mother to her foetus is also possible (Addo et al., 2023). Toxoplasmosis is globally prevalent among humans, varying from region to region and approximately one-third of the world's population is susceptible to infection. Infection is usually asymptomatic in immunocompetent individuals, such as pregnant women and people with HIV (Ali & Al-Warid, 2021). The parasite is

transmitted from an infected pregnant mother to the foetus via the placenta, causing birth defects and miscarriages, especially if infection occurs during the first trimester of pregnancy. In the last three months of pregnancy, it may not cause clinical signs in infants in the early stages of life, but as the child grows older, other signs may develop, for example, chorioretinitis or ophthalmic toxoplasmosis. The severity of the disease is determined by several factors, including the parasite strain, the host's immunity, the type of immune response of the host and the size of the infectious dose (Mahmood et al., 2022). Toxoplasmosis infection leads to abnormalities in some blood components, such as white blood cells and red blood cells and thus to anemia in women (Hassen et al., 2019). Toxoplasmosis infection has also been associated with liver function disorders, as the parasite can affect the activity of liver enzymes (Al-Jowari & Hussein, 2014). Blood lipids of the host are important mediators of the host's defences during the acute phase of innate immunity, infection, and inflammation by various pathogens, for example, bacterial and viral (Al-Kuraishi et al., 2013). The parasite replicates within the host cells in special vacuoles called the parasitic vacuole (PV). This replication requires a large amount of specific lipids for membrane biosynthesis, as it manufactures phospholipids, but it can easily take lipid precursors from the host cells (Al-Khamesi, 2016).

Materials and Methods

Samples Collections

Ninety blood samples were collected from women infected with the *Toxoplasma gondii* parasite between 1-9-2024 and 1-9-2025. The women ranged in age from 18 to 40 years old. The samples were collected at Tikrit Teaching Hospital and several private laboratories in Tikrit. Sixty samples were from women infected with toxoplasmosis, and thirty were from uninfected women. Five millilitres of venous blood were drawn using a 5-mL syringe. The blood sample was then divided into two portions: the first portion (1 mL) was placed in tubes containing EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid), an anticoagulant, for haematological testing (Hb, P.c.v, W.b.c). The second portion (4 mL) was placed in gel tubes and left to stand for 15 minutes to allow for serum separation. The serum was then centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm and withdrawn using a micropipette. The micropipette is stored in small Eppendorf tubes at -4°C until serological tests (liver enzymes and lipids) are performed.

Haematological Tests

Haematological analysis was carried out using an automated haematology analyser (Sysmex CBC) as described by the manufacturer.

Serological Tests

An Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) was used to measure the levels of liver enzymes (AST, ALT and ALP) in the blood serum of individuals infected with the parasite and compare them with the uninfected control group using the Biolab kit, according to the manufacturer's instructions. Lipid profiles (cholesterol, triglycerides and high-density lipoprotein) were also measured using a spectrophotometer, according to the manufacturer's instructions for the Spectra lipid profile kit.

Statistical Analysis

All test data were statistically analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software and a calculator. The analysis relied on a t-test at a probability level of $p \leq 0.001$ to determine the degree of significance of differences between women infected and uninfected with the *Toxoplasma* parasite (Thoemmes, 2012).

Results and Discussion

The Effect of Toxoplasmosis Infection on Blood Tests in Women Infected with the Parasite and Comparison with the Control Group

Measurement of haemoglobin (Hb)

The results of the current study showed a significant decrease in the concentration of haemoglobin (Hb) in women infected with *Toxoplasma gondii* by 9.0 ± 1.6 g/dl compared to the control group by 13.17 ± 1.1 g/dl. Significant differences were recorded at a probability level of $p \leq 0.001$ between the infected group and the control group (Table 1).

Measurement of packed cell volume (P.c.v)

In this study, a significant decrease in P.c.v concentration $35.1 \pm 1.9\%$ was observed in individuals infected with the parasite compared to the control group $39.0 \pm 2.7\%$. Statistical analysis showed significant differences at a $p \leq 0.001$ between the infected and control groups (Table 1).

Measurement of white blood cell count (WBC)

The results of this study showed a significant increase in WBC count 14.3 ± 2.1 in infected individuals compared to uninfected individuals 7.23 ± 1.71 . Statistical analysis showed significant differences at a $p \leq 0.001$ between infected and uninfected individuals (Table 1).

Table 1. Blood Tests in Women Infected with the Parasite *Toxoplasma gondii* Compared with the Control Group

Blood tests	Mean \pm S.D		
	g/dl Hb	P.C.V %	W.B.C $\times 10^3$ /mL
Control	13.17 \pm 1.1	39.0 \pm 2.7	7.23 \pm 1.71
Patients	9.0 \pm 1.6	35.1 \pm 1.9	14.3 \pm 2.1
t-test value	14.5**	6.7**	18.7**

Note: M: mean; S.D: standard deviation; ** indicates the presence of significant differences at the level of $P \leq 0.001$

The results of the current study are consistent with (Al-Taei & Jasim, 2021) in a study conducted on women with toxoplasmosis in Tikrit, which indicated an increase in the number of white blood cells (WBCs). They are also consistent with (Al-Hamdani, 2022), which recorded a significant decrease in haemoglobin concentration (Hb) and blood percentage and a significant increase in the number of white blood cells (WBCs). The results of the current study are consistent with (Mahmood, 2018), a study conducted in Tikrit on pregnant women with toxoplasmosis, in terms of an increase in the number of white blood cells (WBCs) and a decrease in haemoglobin concentration (Hb). The decrease in haemoglobin concentration (Hb) in women with toxoplasmosis is due to recent studies indicating that the prevalence of iron deficiency anaemia during pregnancy worldwide has reached 20% (Garzon et al., 2020). Hence, the reason for the decrease in haemoglobin concentration (Hb) can be attributed to the iron deficiency resulting from the blood, since iron is involved in the structure of haemoglobin (Hb) and therefore, iron deficiency can be the cause of iron deficiency. A decrease in haemoglobin levels and red blood cell count may occur. The reason for the increase in white blood cells may be due to the fact that white blood cells are defensive cells, and any increase in the number of these cells indicates the presence of inflammation in the body. When inflammation occurs in the body or a foreign body, whether it is a virus, bacteria, or a parasite, enters the human body, the immune system will deal with it as a foreign

body, and then the immune system is stimulated. This stimulation, in turn, leads to an increase in the production of white blood cells (Hernández et al., 2021), because white blood cells have the ability to move and engulf foreign bodies (Chmielewski & Strzelec, 2018). Thus, we can conclude that the reason for the increase in the number of white blood cells in women infected with toxoplasmosis may be due to the stimulation of the immune response resulting from the presence of the *Toxoplasma gondii* parasite inside the body.

Effect of Toxoplasma Infection on Liver Enzymes in Infected Women Compared to the Control Group

Measurement of serum Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST) concentration:

The study results showed a significant increase in the average AST enzyme concentration in women infected with *Toxoplasma gondii* 75.78±27.86 ng/ml compared to the control group 2.30±0.81 ng/ml. Significant differences were recorded at a probability level of $p \leq 0.001$ between the infected group and the control group (Table2).

Measurement of Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) enzyme concentration in blood serum:

This study recorded a significant increase in the average concentration of the ALT enzyme in women infected with the parasite 6937.38±2085.61 pg/ml compared to the uninfected control group 391.80±284.10 pg/ml. Statistical analysis showed significant differences at a probability level of $p \leq 0.001$ between the infected group and the control group (Table2).

Measurement of Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) enzyme concentration in blood serum:

This study observed a significant increase in the average concentration of the ALP enzyme 102.34±26.06 ng/ml in women infected with the parasite compared to the control group 22.34±10.46 ng/ml. Statistical analysis showed significant differences at a probability level of $p \leq 0.001$ between the infected group and the control group (Table2).

Table 2. Liver Enzyme Tests in Women Infected with the Parasite *Toxoplasma gondii* Compared with the Control Group

Enzymes	Mean ± S.D		
	AST ng /ml	ALT pg /ml	ALP ng /ml
control	2.30±0.81	391.80±284.10	22.34±10.46
patients	75.78±27.86	6937.38±2085.61	102.34±26.06
t-test value	19.8**	23.98**	20.55**

Note: ** indicates the presence of significant differences at the level of $P \leq 0.001$

The results of the current study are consistent with (Hassoon et al., 2023) and (Jasim & Al-Waaly, 2026), as they recorded a significant increase in the levels of liver enzymes in women infected with the parasite compared to the control group. During a toxoplasmosis infection, several changes occur in the liver that affect the activity of liver enzymes (AST, ALT and ALKP). As a result, these enzymes are used as indicators to assess liver damage caused by toxoplasmosis (Song et al., 2023). The main function of liver enzymes is to transport and store nutrients, metabolise water and electrolytes and remove toxins. The *Toxoplasma gondii* parasite causes liver changes as a result of the multiplication of organisms (Montoya & Liesenfeld, 2004). High concentrations of (AST) and (ALT) indicate hepatocyte necrosis and the level of (ALP) indicates damage to the bile ducts (Babekir et al., 2022).

The Effect of Parasitic Infection on Lipid Profile Tests in Women Infected with the Parasite Compared to Control Groups

Measurement of cholesterol concentration in blood serum

This study recorded a significant increase in the average cholesterol concentration in women infected with the parasite at 230 ± 30 pg/ml compared to non-infected women at 162.7 ± 42.3 pg/ml. The results of the statistical analysis showed significant differences at a probability level of $p \leq 0.001$ between the infected group and the control group (Table 3).

Measurement of Serum Triglyceride Concentration

This study observed a significant increase in the average triglyceride concentration 225.8 ± 33.4 ng/ml in women infected with the parasite compared to women not infected 145.7 ± 9.2 ng/ml. Statistical analysis showed significant differences at a $p \leq 0.001$ level between the infected group and the control group (Table 3).

Measurement of Serum High density lipoprotein (HDL) Concentration

The study results showed a significant increase in the average HDL concentration 38.9 ± 6.1 ng/ml in women infected with *Toxoplasma gondii* 33.7 ± 5.8 ng/ml compared to women not infected with the parasite. Significant differences were recorded at a $p \leq 0.001$ level between the infected group and the control group (Table 3).

Table 3. Lipid Profile Tests in Women Infected with the Parasite Compared to the Control Group

Lipid profile	Mean \pm S.D		
	Cholesterol	Triglyceride	HDL
Control	162.7 \pm 42.3	145.7 \pm 9.2	33.7 \pm 5.8
patients	230 \pm 30	225.8 \pm 33.4	38.9 \pm 6.1
t-test value	7.5**	13.2**	10.3**

Note: ** indicates the presence of significant differences at the level of $P \leq 0.001$

The results of the current study are consistent with those of studies (Sabah & Abed, 2024) and (Al-Azzawi, 2023), which recorded a significant increase in lipid levels in women infected with *Toxoplasma gondii* compared to the control group. Lipids play a crucial role in all aspects of life; they are structural components of cells and participate in metabolic and hormonal pathways (Crook, 2012). They are also important in the defence against parasitic infections, acting as important mediators in the host's defences during the acute phase of the innate immune response. Inflammation and infection clearly alter the host's lipid levels (Feingold & Grunfeld, 2012). Many viral, bacterial and parasitic infections can affect the lipid levels in the blood of infected individuals. Several studies have documented changes in lipid levels during infections with intracellular parasites, such as malaria and visceral leishmaniasis (Taher, 2018). Similarly, HIV-infected patients exhibit changes in certain blood lipid parameters, such as total cholesterol (TC) and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL) (Riddler et al., 2007) and elevated triglycerides (Ghosh, 2018). Lipids are of particular importance to pathogens seeking lipid-rich sites within the host. They enhance lipid availability by stimulating and directing the host. Intracellular pathogens possess complex mechanisms to interfere with and utilise lipid metabolism in host cells. Within parasitic host cells, specialised vacuoles exist and the transfer and flow of lipids between the host and the components of the parasitic vacuole membranes is key to the parasite's success (Crook, 2012). Numerous previous studies have revealed the role of membrane cholesterol in the interaction and binding between the host and the parasite (Vieira et al., 2010). It is an important component of cell membranes in eukaryotic

organisms and plays a critical role in the function and regulation of membrane proteins and receptors. It is essential for the penetration and entry of the parasite into host cells (Coppens et al., 2000). Other studies have proposed the mechanism by which host cholesterol controls entry. The *Toxoplasma* parasite enters the host cells and here the important role of cholesterol in the pathogenesis of toxoplasmosis appears (Coppens & Joiner, 2003).

Conclusions

Toxoplasmosis infection affects several blood parameters, causing a significant decrease in haemoglobin (Hb) and clotting factor (Pvc), along with a significant increase in total white blood cell (Wbc) count in women infected with *Toxoplasma gondii* compared to the uninfected control group.

Tests in women infected with the parasite showed elevated levels of liver enzymes (AST, ALT and ALK) compared to uninfected women with the results showing a significant increase in these levels compared to the control group.

The current study found a significant effect of toxoplasmosis infection on blood lipid levels (cholesterol, triglycerides and high-density lipoprotein) in women compared to the uninfected control group.

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